

ELEMENTS OF CLASS DISTINCTION IN “CURRENTS OF SPACE” BY ISAAC ASIMOV

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ABSTRACT: This article discusses elements of class distinction in American science fiction writer Isaac Asimov’s “Currents of Space”. It provides information about the history of class distinction in our world and how it reflects literature, how author describes class distinction in his work.

KEY WORDS: fiction, symbolic details, genre, spiritual experience, upper, middle and lower classes, racism, slavery.

INTRODUCTION

From the history until now, still we can see elements of class distinctions in our modern society. Class distinction refers to the hierarchical differences between social groups based on their socioeconomic status, which includes factors such as wealth, education, occupation, and social connections. These distinctions often manifest in various aspects of life, such as access to resources, opportunities, and privileges, as well as in cultural practices and lifestyles. The concept is central to the study of social stratification and is a key focus in sociology, economics, and political science.

Historically, class distinctions have been evident in many societies. For example:

- **Feudalism:** Medieval Europe had a rigid class structure with kings, nobles, knights, and serfs.
- **Caste System:** In India, the caste system created hereditary classes that dictated one's occupation and social interactions.

MAIN PART

Social class is a grouping of people that divided into the upper, middle and lower classes. Isaac Asimov, a prolific science fiction writer and biochemist, often explored themes of racism and prejudice in his works.[1] While he did not write extensively on the topic in his non-fiction, his fiction often addressed these issues indirectly through allegory and metaphor. For example in his

Robot Series:

- **Robots and Human Prejudice:** In his Robot series, Asimov created a society where robots, despite their capabilities, were treated with suspicion and often subjected to prejudice by humans. This can be seen as

an allegory for racism, where an "other" group, in this case, robots, faces discrimination based on irrational fears and biases.

- **Laws of Robotics:** The Three Laws of Robotics, designed to protect humans, also reflect a deeper commentary on control and subjugation, mirroring how societal rules can both protect and oppress marginalized groups.

Foundation Series:

- **Galactic Society:** In the Foundation series, Asimov depicted a vast galactic society with numerous planets and cultures. The series addresses the complexity of cultural and racial diversity, often showing how biases and prejudices can impact political and social structures.
- **Seldon Crisis:** The recurring theme of societal crises and the need for adaptive, inclusive solutions can be interpreted as a call for overcoming entrenched prejudices and working towards a more equitable society.

Short Stories:

- **"The Ugly Little Boy":** This story explores the theme of prejudice against a Neanderthal child brought to the present through time travel, highlighting the irrationality and cruelty of discrimination based on physical differences.
- **"The Bicentennial Man":** The story of a robot striving to become human touches on themes of identity, acceptance, and the struggle against prejudice.

In addition, this kind of problem is seen in his another work "The Currents of Space" with elements of racism, slavery and others. As for the "anti-racist theme" that Pringle mentions, it is surely there, with kyrt standing in for cotton, and the Florinians the slaves to their Sarkite masters. Junz, a black man from the predominantly black planet of Libair (read:Liberia), denounces the Sark/Florina political and cultural situation at several opportunities.[2]

Historically, there are many different types of slavery including chattel, bonded, forced labour and sexual slavery. The key characteristics of slavery are ones generally agreed such as the loss of freedom of movement and legal rights. In the ancient world, slavery developed for a number of reasons including economic necessity especially in civilizations and agricultural economies where larger workforces were needed. Domination was another factor.[3] War produced not only spoils such as gold but also people to take as slaves which eventually also became a form of status symbol. The more slaves you had, the wealthier and more influential you were.

The inhabitants of the planet Florina harvest "kyrt," which can be made into the most desirable cloth in the galaxy. For some reason, kyrt can *only* be grown on Florina: people have tried taking kyrt seeds to other planets and reproducing the exact environmental conditions of Florina, but everywhere else in the galaxy, it is just cotton. That is why, The Sark planet occupy the Florina. Local people of Florina became slave in their own planet for the sarkities.

Florina itself is divided into two part: Upper city and Lower city. In addition, there is the matter of the Lower City and the Upper City in Rik's town. While the Lower City houses the poor indigenous populace, the Upper City, 30 feet overhead, features a luxurious wonderland of sorts for the Sark Squires. In other words, complete segregation, which the author castigates time and again.

There was a big huge beautiful library in the Florina, but local people cannot go to the library. Still most of the local people were illiterate.

- "Terens gave him a quick, surprised glance. He had been accustomed to all this on Sark, but he, too, found the garishness of Upper City somewhat vulgar. But then, Upper City was more Sark than Sark itself. On Sark, not all men were aristocrats. There were even poor Sarkites, some scarcely better off than the average Florinian. Here only the top of the pyramid existed, and the library showed that." [4]

- "To any Florinian, of course, Captain Racety would have been a "Squire." Simply that. To any Florinian, all Sarldtes were Squires. But to the Sarkites there were Squires and real Squires. The Captain was simply a Squire. Samia of Fife was a real Squire; or the feminine equivalent of one, which amounted to the same thing." [4]

It does not matter, whether you are poor or rich sarkites, still your position is higher from Florinians. Florinians can only work in menial jobs. Only a descendant of Florinians may qualify for the position of resident, but still the status of a resident is lower than a simple squire.

Asimov's personal views on racism were progressive for his time. He believed in equality and often used his platform to advocate for rational thinking and against bigotry. His writings reflect a belief in the potential for humanity to overcome its prejudices through reason and understanding.

In interviews and essays, Asimov emphasized the importance of science and education in combating ignorance and prejudice. He argued that much of racism stemmed from ignorance and fear of the unknown, and that education and exposure to different cultures could help reduce these biases.

CONCLUSION:

Isaac Asimov's work often tackled the issues of racism and prejudice through science fiction narratives, using robots, aliens, and future societies as metaphors for human societal issues. His belief in rationality, education, and the fundamental equality of all beings is evident in his storytelling and his personal philosophy. Asimov's legacy includes a powerful critique of racism and a hopeful vision for a more inclusive future..

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